

Report on e-infrastructure evaluation

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Summary and conclusions

Relevant cloud technologies ranging from Infrastructure-as-a-Service (OpenStack) to two types of Platform-as-a-Service solutions (MQTT, Apache Airflow) were evaluated. Using the SAPP acquisition and preprocessing system as a testbed we discovered that for complex systems such as SAPP it is important that the software is built to support the virtualisation environment instead of being retrofitted into it. Here the cloud technology would solve issues related to hardware acquisition and maintenance, but could introduce additional problems due to mismatches between the software distribution and the platform. In this case a container based approach was considered to be the better future alternative for IaaS usage.

Message passing (MQ) technology based on the MQTT standard was evaluated for aggregating real time data flows. Scalability and reliability was found to be good and the approach seems viable for converting real time data flows into a format that is easier to connect to batch based data processing pipelines. Relying on MQ as a service would offload a critical and challenging component to the cloud provider, internal or external, allowing the e-Infrastructure implementor to focus on the processing logic.

The popular workflow engine Apache Airflow was evaluated for processing data flows to NWP. Also, machine learning methods, possibly running on an HPC environment, were integrated into the workflow. Airflow was found to perform well. If a workflow engine was used as a cloud service, then many challenging questions related to scalability and reliability could be moved to the cloud provider. As an example, it is difficult to ascertain that certain workflows are always run and run only once, regardless of component failures and other lower level problems. Not having to deal with these questions in data processing scripts could be considered a major improvement.

Objective

This document reports the results of e-infrastructure evaluation performed in Work Package 5 (WP5) of the Improved Observation Usage in NWP (iOBS) project. The work package was formulated to evaluate how future e-infrastructure for numerical weather prediction (NWP) could make use of cloud and high-performance computing (HPC) resources. New kinds of computing infrastructure is needed to tackle challenges coming

from both data ingestion from non-conventional (private) data sources and integration of machine learning components to standard IT systems. As HPC has always been central to NWP this work focused primarily on possibilities of cloud technologies. Work was conducted in collaboration with other work packages of the project, especially with WP1 and WP2.

Cloud technologies are not yet widely used in numerical weather prediction. The idea behind cloud computing is to turn IT infrastructure into a service that is easier to take into use and maintain. Cloud services are typically supported by large scale centralised data centers and they are operated by external cloud service providers, but can also be offered internally and supported by on-premises IT infrastructure (private cloud). NWP is typically a critical task carried out by national meteorological institutions, having different types of security and integrity considerations. Hence, private clouds are the most relevant candidate given these requirements and were in the focus of this project.

Cloud technologies are categorised by the type of service they can be used to provide. Most common categories are Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS), Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) and Software-as-a-Service (SaaS). IT infrastructure such as servers can be replaced by an IaaS cloud, where one can e.g. deploy virtual machines on the cloud environment without needing to work with hardware. The PaaS concept raises the abstraction level by providing various types of runtime and computing engines, such as high level programming and data management environments. Finally, SaaS is about providing the application itself as a cloud service and it is a concept familiar to all through popular cloud applications such as Google Docs and Slack. SaaS is mostly relevant for popular applications created for the general audience. For NWP the potential technologies for future e-Infrastructures were identified to primarily come from IaaS and PaaS categories, as the required software is very specific.

In this work package three technology evaluations were performed. In the IaaS category the approach was easy to define: evaluate a relevant piece of a modern data ingestion pipeline on an IaaS cloud environment. For the purposes of iOBS, this was the SAPP¹ acquisition and pre-processing system developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). This work package collaborated with WP1 to set up the SAPP system on the OpenStack² IaaS virtualisation environment operated by CSC.

For the PaaS category, we needed to consider the main challenges related to data pipelines. Data flows can be divided into two types: continuous (stream) and intermittent

¹ <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/elibrary/17341-sapp-new-scalable-acquisition-and-pre-processing-system-ecmwf>

² <https://www.openstack.org>

(batches). Based on this division the work package was designed to address most relevant technologies for both cases. Data streams and other high-frequency data sources are most often handled with message queue technologies in the cloud setting, with perhaps the strongest development currently being in the Internet of Things (IoT) area. Therefore, the MQTT standard³ was chosen as a popular and IoT oriented option and Eclipse Mosquitto⁴ implementation of the standard was used to evaluate aggregating real time data flows.

Batch data processing is often implemented with extract-transform-load (ETL) or workflow engines. As ETL is more targeted for normalised and very structured databases, we considered workflows engines more suitable for processing somewhat raw observation data. Hence, we evaluated a popular workflow engine (Apache Airflow⁵) in processing typical data flows for NWP and also integrating machine learning methods, possibly running on HPC environment, into the workflows.

Evaluation: SAPP on OpenStack IaaS

SAPP is an acquisition and pre-processing system developed by ECMWF. In WP1 of the iOBS project SAPP was evaluated for numerical weather prediction among participating meteorological institutes. In WP5 we extended the evaluation to study how an IaaS cloud environment could be used to host the SAPP system. We used CSC's cPouta cloud which is based on OpenStack virtualisation technology. Similar services on the public clouds are Amazon EC2 and Azure compute services.

The evaluation was done between 11/2019 and 1/2020. During that period SAPP was distributed as virtual machine images (open virtual appliance, OVA). It was primarily intended to be run with VirtualBox virtualisation technology and as such, was not directly deployable to OpenStack. In general, using virtual machine images for software system distribution can be considered somewhat problematic.

In our evaluation, the following steps were needed to make SAPP distribution work in OpenStack, or in other words, "cloudify" the distribution:

- OVA image was extracted into two VM disk images
- fstab and symbolic link entries were updated
- Images were merged to a single qcow2 formatted file
- At this point the virtual machine was bootable, but SAPP was not running

³ <https://mqtt.org>

⁴ <https://mosquitto.org>

⁵ <https://airflow.apache.org>

- ECMWF's Virtual Machine Tutorial⁶ was followed to set up SAPP

To verify operation of SAPP we followed two ECMWF tutorials:

- Data Flow Tutorial⁷
- How-to Acquire, process and extract GTS data⁸

In the end, we were able to process and extract WMO GTS (Global Telecommunication System) data provided by MET Norway. The installation passed the simple smoke tests and was functional. However, it turned out there were serious stability issues that prevented large-scale use of the installation.

Identified problems were:

- In general, there were many references to ECMWF internal network in e.g. authorised SSH keys and network proxy configurations, which needed to be fixed
- yum repositories were not working, likely due to network configuration problems, preventing installation of software
- Somewhat periodically the VM went into a bad state and started to give Input/Output error messages for most command line operations. This was caused by disk driver problems and could be fixed with full restart.
- Fixing the disk problem would have required better diagnostics tools to be installed, which again was blocked by previously mentioned problems.

In conclusion, it was possible to deploy SAPP from the OVA image to the OpenStack environment. As this was not the intended form of deployment, it led to a large number of problems and made the installation useful only for simple trials. It would have been a major effort to make the OVA image completely "cloudified" and reliable on our OpenStack environment. We argue the root causes for these issues were: 1) virtual machine images in general are primarily meant to save and move system state inside a virtualisation environment or environments of same type, not for portability between any virtualisation environments, 2) virtual machine images in general are problematic as devices of software distribution as they capture a lot of the surrounding context of the software installations, 3) OVA images were meant for VirtualBox and had to be retrofitted to OpenStack.

⁶ <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=140378666>

⁷ <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=140385303>

⁸ <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/SAPP/Acquire%2C+process+and+extract+GTS+data>

Our suggestion is that the issues should not be fixed in the deployment phase, but earlier in the software development and release pipeline by changing the way SAPP software is bundled and distributed. The new container based distribution of the system addresses these issues and can be considered as a promising development. Containers can be seen as the ideal solution for distributing systems such as SAPP for use in modern cloud environments. They can be run on top of virtual machine based IaaS environments, including OpenStack, or deployed to a container based IaaS such as Kubernetes or OpenShift.

Evaluation: Realtime data on MQTT (PaaS)

Message queues are a typical service in a modern cloud stack. Public clouds provide solutions such as Amazon SQS and Azure Service Bus. The rise of Internet of Things (IoT) networks of sensors and such is a recent driver for messaging technologies. In the context of iOBS similar challenges could be faced when integrating private weather stations. The aim of this evaluation is to test message queues and simple data handling methods for streaming observation data, as they could prove useful for tackling the technical challenges coming from non-conventional (private) data sources.

The purpose of this task was to create and test suitable means to slow down fast streaming observation data to the level where processing capacity of databases and the like is sufficient. The required stream data rate conversion in its simplest form can be done by aggregating high-frequency data samples and then re-sampling the aggregated results at the desired lower data rate. The basic idea is depicted in the following figure.

Figure: Principle for handling streaming observation data. Fast data is aggregated and resampled at a lower rate.

A suitable algorithm for data aggregation can be as an example statistical moving average or median, depending on the observation data. The data handling methods can also e.g. perform QC instead of slowing down the fast data stream.

Message queue (message broker) was used as a base for our stream handler. For this evaluation a message broker can be thought of as an intermediary used for delivering any kind of messages between a sender and recipient(s). There are several suitable message queue platforms and building blocks which can be used for this kind of message delivering purposes. Important examples include:

- Apache Kafka: An open-source stream-processing software platform. Very powerful but excessive for evaluation purposes
- Redis: Not only a database but also a message broker running in RAM without a need for direct hard drive access and thus very fast. Somewhat excessive for evaluation purposes.
- MQTT: A lightweight, publish-subscribe network protocol. It is widely used for e.g. transporting sensor data in the IoT context.

MQTT was chosen as a base for our test environment. There are numerous MQTT message queue implementations available, including Apache ActiveMQ (requires Java environment), RabbitMQ (requires Erlang environment) and Eclipse Mosquitto. For this evaluation Eclipse Mosquitto was used.

MQTT's mode of operation is on a par with e.g. Slack communication platform; at first you must subscribe to (cf. Slack's "join") a topic or topics (cf. "channel" or "channels") and after that you can publish (cf. "send") messages including text, images and so forth to the topic. All subscribers (cf. "members") on that topic ("channel") will receive the messages sent by any subscriber/member.

MQTT messages can be addressed to different data hierarchy levels by using a slash ("/") as a separating character in a topic, so the topics that will be formed can be for instance "Oulu / wind / 3s" and "Oulu / wind / 10min". The publish-subscribe model allows data handling modules to connect streaming observation data by subscribing to a relevant topic, receiving data messages, and then in turn publish their results as new messages into the same topic or another one.

In the following figure the streaming observation data is publishing its content into a topic named "stream/z". Data handling functions, such as mean and median join the stream by subscribing the topic "stream/z" and they publish their calculated results repeatedly in a topic named "mean/60s" and "median/60s", respectively. The topic

names in this case are just examples and they can be defined ad hoc at application level.

Figure: Data messages between senders and recipients. The system consists of observation data streams (1 and 2), data handling functions (3 and 4) and data users (5). Messages are passed by the broker between the consecutive steps.

The system architecture was designed and implemented keeping in mind that it will act only as a proof of concept, i.e. the same principle could also be implemented using another messaging protocol.

The proof-of-concept system was programmed with Python and JavaScript languages with a few hundred code lines. The code is organised as threads in order to be able to execute the calculation functions and the rest of the software concurrently.

We implemented the architecture and ran an experimental demonstration. The experiment procedure was to start different kinds of processing units and then verify their outputs. We found it quite difficult and laborious to find any suitable streaming data sources which would be available and fast enough for our purposes. So, we relied on a simulator i.e. a data stream generator for input data. The demonstration software is

available for the project participants on request and is being made available on Gitlab provided by CodeRefinery.

Many different scenarios and types of data aggregation were tested. All the timings and the calculated results were exactly as expected. While running this experiment on a laptop the total CPU usage for the test related processes was approximately 1 % and the memory footprint was about 0.5 % out of 3 GB i.e. less than 20 MB. The experiment and its results are described in more detail on task report 5.2, which is available on the project's Google Drive folder.

As a conclusion, the experiments did not reveal any signs of technical threats or performance problems related to the architecture, suggesting that this could be a viable solution for real time data aggregation.

Evaluation: Workflows with Apache Airflow (PaaS)

Workflow engines are a natural fit for implementing data processing pipelines. Public cloud platforms provide services such as Amazon SWF and Azure Logic Apps. The goal of this evaluation was to see how the popular open source Apache Airflow workflow engine could be used as a PaaS cloud environment where data flows related to numerical weather prediction and integration of machine learning models trained in a HPC computing environment could be easily implemented. In this evaluation we did not consider real time data flows.

The designed and evaluated infrastructure is illustrated in the figure below:

Figure: Diagram showing the movement of data between workflow stages. Data flows from left to right: data from both conventional weather stations as well as personal NetAtmo stations are gathered from different sources, pushed to a centralised database

and fed forward to machine learning models that produce a list of reliable NetAtmo stations. This list is then used to filter the original raw data, leaving only data from reliable stations that can then be used for weather prediction.

Introduction to Apache Airflow

Apache Airflow is an open source Python library to programmatically author, schedule and monitor workflows. Airflow can be used to define different kinds of tasks, set dependencies between them and then automate the execution of these tasks. Tasks can be anything that can be achieved programmatically, such as creating a certain file, running an analysis or a machine learning model, or moving data in or out of a database. It is similar in functionality to the workflow package ecFlow developed by ECMWF, but has a significantly larger user base.

Airflow's main purpose is to act as a glue between different kinds of tasks that need to be run, instead of being used to define the actual tasks. Airflow's goal is to ensure that a certain task is run when it is supposed to and provide fault tolerance measures as well as ways to monitor the execution of the tasks. Examples of these are retrying tasks if they fail, possibility to configure Airflow to send an email to a specified address if a task is retried or has failed, as well as a web user interface that has plenty of visualisations and graphs of the workflow pipelines and their current state.

Airflow also has a wide variety of integrations to other systems. There are multiple operators that can execute tasks in different environments, executing for example any Bash or Python script or a Jupyter Notebook. Airflow also provides a selection of hooks that connect easily to different external systems such as MySQL, S3 or Apache Spark. If a certain operator or hook is not provided by Airflow, it is possible to create a custom one by extending their existing base classes.

Apache Airflow in iOBS

The workflow that was implemented in Airflow consisted of gathering the weather data from different sources, transforming it according to our needs and storing it to our database. Finally data is fed to machine learning models for quality control.

The workflow was split into several pipelines (or DAGs, as they are called in Airflow) to achieve the goal. Different DAGs were produced to test different ways of obtaining weather data from different producers: two to collect data from open data APIs, and one to collect data that was streamed to an object store from MET Norway. Furthermore, two

DAGs running machine learning models with the gathered data were produced, one running a kriging model and one running a model based on clustering.

Airflow turned out to be a powerful workflow management tool that is fairly easy to use. The wide variety of integrations ensure that it's possible to achieve the wanted results using the technology or coding languages that are best suited for the job, and connect a variety of scripts and platforms to a reliably working logical whole. As the DAGs are defined in Python code, it's easy to manage using version control tools such as Git, and collaboratively develop them if necessary. Airflow has worked reliably, and as it is developed by a very active community, it's likely to get even better in the future.

While this infrastructure was developed using Airflow version 1.10.x, during the development Airflow 2.0 was released. Unfortunately, the possibilities of the version 2.0 had to be left out of the evaluation.

All of the code of the DAGs developed in this evaluation is available in Gitlab provided by CodeRefinery.

OpenShift as deployment platform

We deployed an Airflow instance running the developed pipelines using CSC's OpenShift platform Rahti. OpenShift is an open source container application platform, based on the Kubernetes container orchestrator.

As OpenShift applications are run as containers, a container image that had Airflow installed and was compatible with the OpenShift platform had to be developed. This was done before Airflow started offering an official container image developed by the Airflow community, so deploying Airflow using containers should be less cumbersome now given that there is an official image.

To ease deployment of Airflow in OpenShift, also an OpenShift template was produced that sets up an application running Airflow, complete with all needed configurations such as connection to Airflow's internal database.

Deploying Airflow on OpenShift resulted in a robust workflow management system that could automatically recover from most failures both in the infrastructure (hardware or container failures) and in the workflows (task failures). Monitoring the state of the workflows is easy, as both OpenShift and Airflow have a web user interface with extensive visualisations about the state of the application or the workflows. Setting up

deployment with the developed OpenShift template was easy and fast, resulting in a running Airflow instance with a well working configuration.

Data sources

Two different kinds of methods to obtain the weather data were tested. One method was to contact publicly open APIs of meteorological institutes: the data was extracted by pulling it regularly from the APIs, transforming it according to our needs and then stored in our own database. The other method was to set up data pipelines straight from the meteorological institutes to an object storage system, where the data could be pulled from. As data streamed from the Norwegian meteorological institute was in the compressed BUFR file format, the data had to be decoded. We experimented with two libraries, ecCodes and PyBufKit. Working with BUFR proved to be difficult and error-prone, but still we managed to implement proof-of-concept pipelines that process BUFR data.

As publicly open APIs are designed to be understandable, coding against them is easy, and it doesn't require a lot of code to get the wanted data out of them. However, this solution requires that such an API exists, works reliably and is maintained. It might also be that the data that is available from APIs is already "diluted down", and there might not be access to all data that is of interest.

Setting up a pipeline from the meteorological institute obviously requires some extra effort from the institute, as well as an intermediary data storage solution, but potentially leads to a more robust system that doesn't depend on the API in the middle. This pipeline could also be tailored to send more relevant data than a general-purpose API.

Data storage on centralised database

In order to store the weather data that was harvested from multiple sources, a database server was set up to store all the data in a unified format.

measurements		stations	
timestamp	datetime	station_id	varchar
station_id	varchar	type	int
type	int	lon	float
temp	float	lat	float
humidity	float	alt	float
pressure	float	valid	tinyint

Figure: Schema of the two database tables. Table “measurements” stores the timestamp, station id, type of the station (NetAtmo or any of the conventional producers of weather data such as FMI), temperature, humidity and pressure of a measurement, while table “stations” stores station id, type of the station, longitude, latitude and altitude of the station, as well as the validity (station was marked invalid if its longitude or latitude changes: this applies primarily to NetAtmo stations).

Timestamp, station id and type of the station were all chosen as primary keys for the “measurements” table to easily ensure that no duplicates of the measurements were entered to the database. The “stations” table has two primary keys, station id and type of station: station id might not be a strong enough primary key if two different types of stations happen to have the same station id.

The database was a MySQL database server running on a virtual machine on CSC’s cloud service cPouta. This might not be a scalable enough solution, as the amount of data gathered gets large fairly quickly. In order to deal with the amount of data, some alternative solutions could be considered, such as deleting older data from the database, or setting up a distributed, more scalable database system such as Apache HBase or Apache Cassandra that can store larger amounts of data.

While collected and transformed weather data was stored in a relational database, other data storage needs were handled with CSC’s data store Allas, which is an S3 compatible object storage system powered by Ceph. Allas served as the intermediary storage for storing the GTS data stream coming from the Norwegian meteorological

institute, as well as the place for storing the final filtered data. S3 API worked reliably and was easy to use for this purpose.

It could also be possible to not use a relational database at all and also handle the storing of the extracted weather data in S3. Originally the database was chosen to store the weather data to enable flexible queries of the data, while the ultimate needs for the queries were shaping up during the development. If it is clear how often the models are run with what data, it should be considered whether to store the data only in S3 in convenient batches and read the data directly from there, sparing the maintainers of the infrastructure from setting up and maintaining a database server.

Machine learning pipelines

The data gathered to the database was put into use with two daily running DAGs that collected the data from the previous 24 hours from the database and ran quality control machine learning models with the data. The two models integrated into the system were a model using kriging and a model based on clustering called netatmoqc. Both produced a list of NetAtmo stations that the models saw as reliable, producing valid data. When the models finished computation, the produced list of reliable stations were used to filter the original data, resulting in better quality data. This data was finally transformed to the OBSOUL format and stored.

A major challenge for the models was the amount of data. In this setting the daily amount of NetAtmo observations that had to be processed reached ca. 7,5 million observations, resulting in a task that could be characterised as a big data problem. When running the models with all of the NetAtmo data from the past 24 hours, the pipeline running times, consisting of pre-processing the data for the model and running the model, reached around 12 hours. To prevent processes running out of memory and getting killed, some heavy memory-saving configurations of the models were needed, possibly resulting in sub-optimal computational results. It could have been beneficial to design all elements of the pipeline to take the amount of data into account from the start and utilise horizontal scaling more efficiently with technologies such as Apache Spark. In this evaluation the existing parallelisation features and possibilities of the models were not studied further.

In the evaluation it became evident how machine learning methods were developed separately, without consideration on how to ultimately integrate them with the Airflow pipeline. This resulted in different approaches to what kind of data and in what form is given to the model, which resulted in a bit of compatibility issues and extra code to suit

different needs. While this was not a big problem, some agreements on the data format and taking into account the integration of the machine learning models already in the development phase could have helped to produce a more lean system. This way the computation times could also be shortened, when the large amount of data doesn't have to be transformed as often.